

Education Curicullum in Indonesia and South Korea

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ABSTRACT: Education systems in Indonesia and Korea differed from each other. Each one contains differences that can be compared, which resulted from the Korean Educational System. Because of its very high level of education, Korea is a model nation for Indonesia's educational system. Among these, the most important is that each differs greatly in literacy, educational facilities, and learning time. The condition may become more brittle if the Indonesian educational system experiences growth and change. It is considered a reform of education, which means that every person in the community has a common experience with schooling. Developments and changes to the education system in Indonesia can reduce the level of conditions. This can be seen as the existence of educational reform, which means that every person in society has equal access to education at school. The result of educational reform, which means that everyone in society has equal access to education at school.

KEYWORDS: Education, level of Literacy, facility, learning times

INTRODUCTION

The quality of individuals in a country reflects the quality of education they receive. Education plays an important role in improving the quality and morals of every citizen as a member of a civilized nation. Through quality education, educated individuals who will become pillars in developing the country will be formed. The success of an effective education system is key in preparing the young generation to face global challenges.

According to Soekidjo Notoatmodjo, education is a planned effort to change other people, be they individuals, groups, or society, so that they can do what educational practitioners expect. According to the Language Center of the Ministry of National Education, education is a process of changing a person's or group's attitudes and behavior through teaching and training, aiming to develop human maturity. John Stuart Mill stated that education includes all actions carried out by individuals for themselves or others to bring them closer to perfection. Ki Hajar Dewantara, an Indonesian education figure, describes education as a conscious effort to prepare students through guidance, teaching, and training to be ready to play their role in the future.

The importance of the educational curriculum as a fundamental pillar in directing and improving the quality of a country's education cannot be doubted. Indonesia and South Korea, rich in history and culture, show striking differences in their approaches to the education system. By comparing educational curricula in these two countries, we can identify differences in curriculum structure, learning focus, teaching methods, and efforts made to improve the overall quality of education.

Indonesia, as an archipelagic country with great cultural and ethnic diversity, has unique challenges in developing an educational curriculum that reflects this diversity. The education curriculum in Indonesia has undergone several significant changes, especially since the 2003 education reform, which aims to increase the relevance, quality, and accessibility of education. The 2013 curriculum is an important milestone in changing Indonesian education by integrating a scientific approach, character education, and an emphasis on developing 21st-century skills.

On the other hand, South Korea has been in the international spotlight because of its success in achieving high educational standards. South Korea's educational curriculum reflects its commitment to innovation and technology, with a strong focus on mathematics, science, and information technology. South Korea's education system is also known for its competitive approach and rigorous standardized tests, which are integral to their learning culture.

The differences and similarities between educational curricula in Indonesia and South Korea and their impact on student learning and development. By understanding these differences, we can learn valuable lessons to improve the education systems in these two countries and develop best practices that can be applied globally.

METHOD

In writing this article, the method used is Literature Review. Literature Review is research on scientific articles, books, and other sources that are relevant to a particular problem, research field, or theory, as well as several other documents that have been

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published.¹ The author uses this method to review and identify journals in a structured manner, following the procedures set out for each step. The author identifies relevant literature sources related to the research topic, namely a comparison of the education curriculum education system in Indonesia and the education curriculum in South Korea.

DISCUSSION AND RESEARCH FINDINGS

Education Curriculum in Indonesia

The education curriculum is important as a guide to achieving educational goals. The National Education System Law defines the curriculum as a series of plans that include objectives, content, learning materials, and learning methods that serve as guidelines for the learning process to achieve certain educational goals (Law No. 20 of 2013 Article 1 paragraph 9).² The curriculum is a learning plan prepared by educational institutions for students, which aims to direct their growth and development by the academic goals set. Since 1945, the educational curriculum has undergone several changes in the history of Indonesian education. These changes occurred in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1975, 1984, 1994, 2004, and 2006, and the most recent are the 2013 and Merdeka curricula. The history of education is considered an important part of human life. Changes in the curriculum are caused by changes in society's political, socio-cultural, economic, and technological systems. The curriculum needs to be adjusted dynamically to the needs and changes that occur in society, based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. The curriculum is also considered a guide in teaching and learning. The curriculum needs to be continuously updated.

The first curriculum during independence was called the 1947 Lesson Plan. Initially, the more commonly used term was "leer plan" rather than "curriculum" in English. The educational principle held is Pancasila. However, due to the unstable political situation resulting from the Revolutionary War, the 1947 Lesson Plan was only implemented in 1950, often called the 1950 curriculum. The structure is simple, only including a list of subjects, teaching hours, and teaching outlines. This year, the curriculum in Indonesia is still influenced by the Dutch and Japanese colonial education systems. The content of the 1947 curriculum prioritizes character and behavior education in humans with their awareness and daily life. Through the 1947 curriculum, Indonesia has a strategic role in uniting the nation through education.

In 1952, the Indonesian curriculum was refined by changing its name to the 1952 detailed learning plan. One of the main characteristics of this curriculum is the emphasis on the connection between lesson content and daily life, which emphasizes the nation's values and morals. The concept of curriculum objectives shows a strong humanist approach, where the subject matter connected to daily life aims to shape students' attitudes and behaviour based on human values. It is hoped that students can implement these values in various situations at school, in their families, in communities, and abroad. The importance of forming an open, selfless attitude and mutual respect in students is an effort to integrate essential cultural values into everyday life. The lesson material also covers aspects of life that are ethical and responsible and can be used as an example.³ The advantage of the 1952 curriculum is that the curriculum is more detailed, the subject syllabus is clear, and a teacher only teaches one subject. Community classes are also formed to teach skills so that children who cannot afford to go to junior high school can go straight to work.

In 1964, the government updated the curriculum system with the 1964 Education Plan. This curriculum emphasizes the importance of society acquiring academic knowledge, especially at the elementary school level. Learning focuses on the Pancawardhana program and includes moral, intellectual, emotional or artistic development, skills and physical fitness. This curriculum, known as the 1964 Education Plan or 1964 Curriculum, appeared towards the end of President Sukarno's term of office. The main theme that appears in this curriculum is an active, creative and productive learning approach. This approach requires schools to teach students to independently think of solutions to problems. The learning method used is called guided cooperation. In addition, the government designated Saturday as Kurida Day, allowing students to participate freely in culture, arts, sports, and games according to their interests.⁴ The 1964 curriculum focuses on developing creativity, taste, initiative, work and morals, known as Pancawardhana. The learning approach also emphasizes a learning approach that encourages students to be active and independent. Meanwhile, the 1952 curriculum focused more on academic knowledge and basic skills, and the 1952 curriculum also did not yet link the subject matter much to everyday life.

The 1968 curriculum is a form of renewal of the 1964 curriculum, namely changing the structure of the curriculum from Pancawardhana to fostering the spirit of Pancasila. This curriculum emphasises efforts to form true Pancasila people who are strong, physically healthy, moral, and have good character and religious beliefs. The number of lessons from this curriculum has nine main subjects and only theoretical material without linking it to actual problems in the surrounding environment. The advantage of this curriculum compared to the previous curriculum is that it is political and focuses more on the formation of true Pancasila people.

¹Zulia Putri Perdani et al., *Panduan Literature Review* (Yogyakarta: PT.Nas Media Indonesia, 2021),hal 1.

²Rony S .Y Zebua, *Potret Perkembangan Kurikulum Pendidikan Indonesia Dari Masa Ke Masa* (Jakarta: Magister Pendidikan Islam UNISBA, 2020), hal 1.

³Asfiati, *Pendekatan Humanis Dalam Pengembangan Kurikulum* (Medan: Perdana Publishing, 2016), hal 28.

⁴Achmad Zaeni and Nurul Husna Mustika sari dkk, *Kurikulum Pada Pembelajaran Di Madrasah* (Jawa Tengah: Penerbit NEM, 2023), hal 19.

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The 1975 Curriculum aims to make education more efficient and effective. The 1975 curriculum is an improvement from the 1968 curriculum, which focuses on processes. However, the 1975 curriculum emphasizes achieving educational goals in a centralized manner while still paying attention to the process and achieving academic goals that are more equitable and fair. The 1975 curriculum has the advantage of the 1968 curriculum because it places greater emphasis on the formation of human character who is sovereign and equal to other nations.⁵

The 1984 curriculum resulted from a political decision that replaced the 1975 curriculum. Influenced by Humanistic psychology, its approach emphasized active students in learning. Instructional objectives become the main focus, with a learning approach emphasizing process skills. The material is presented spirally to ensure understanding before practice and adapted to the student readiness level. The 1984 Curriculum, a refinement of the 1975 Curriculum, is superior in developing process skills, clear curriculum structure, and increasing important lesson hours.⁶

The 1994 curriculum results are a combination of the 1975 and 1984 curricula. It was implemented by Law No. 2 of 1989 concerning the National Education System. The change from the semester to a quarterly system aims to allow students to absorb the material better. However, according to research, the dense national and local content and the diverse interests of society make this curriculum less successful, with less than satisfactory results. The advantage of this curriculum is that the curriculum material is fully available, so teachers can arrange the lessons to be taught. Each subject has its structure, so it is easy for teachers to change it.⁷

The competency-based curriculum includes competency standards and core competencies for each subject. Competency standards are defined as the completeness of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and proficiency in subjects. The changing curriculum became a competency-based curriculum (KBK) in 1994 aimed to improve the quality of education in Indonesia. KBK is designed to provide survival skills and expertise to anticipate life changes, conflict, uncertainty and difficulties due to the impact of globalization. In other words, KBK can offer solutions to students who utilize learning materials in everyday life. KBK emphasizes student-centred learning to help students reach their maximum potential and achieve national education goals set out in the National Education System Law.⁸

The implementation of the Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP) follows the provisions stated in Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards. KTSP was developed by referring to eight national standards set by the National Education Standards Agency (BSNP), including Graduate Competency Standards, Content Standards, Facilities and Infrastructure Standards, Management Standards, Educational Financing Standards, and Educational Assessment Standards. However, KTSP and Competency Based Curriculum (KBK) have slight differences in terms of substance, learning development approach, target achievement, and evaluation process. The main difference lies in the authority given to each school to design educational plans that suit the needs of students and their environment while still referring to national standards. As stated by Dhaifi, KTSP places more emphasis on the local aspect of education. In developing the KTSP curriculum, each school considers mandatory content, local content, and self-development in an integrated manner, as well as paying attention to the diversity of students and environmental conditions without distinguishing between religion, ethnicity, culture, customs, social status, or gender.⁹ The advantage of this curriculum is that it uses a competency approach that focuses on understanding, abilities or qualities, especially in schools that work in relation to the surrounding community. Competency standards that focus on individual abilities, learning skills and socio-cultural background and teachers as facilitators whose job is to facilitate student learning. The ability-based approach places students in a process of continuous development of all aspects of their personality. It develops their innate potential in accordance with the learning opportunities provided by the existing environment.¹⁰

The 2013 Curriculum is a refinement of the 2006 Education Unit Level Curriculum, which is directed at anticipating the competency needs of the 21st century by focusing on students' observation, questioning, reasoning and communication skills after they receive the lesson material. The preparation of the 2013 Curriculum is a continuation of the development of the Competency-Based Curriculum (KBK), which began in 2004.¹¹ The advantages of the 2013 Curriculum include various aspects: students are encouraged to be more active, creative and innovative in facing challenges at school; Assessment covers all aspects, including grades, morals, religion, practice and attitudes, not just exams. Character and manners education has been integrated into all study

⁵Yayah Huliatusna dkk, *Dasar Pengembangan Kurikulum Sekolah Dasar*, 2022, hal 38.

⁶Yayah Yuliatusna dkk, *Dasar Pengembangan Kurikulum Sekolah Dasar* (Jawa barat: CV jejak (jejak publisher), 2022), hal 129.

⁷Ismatul Maula and Ermelinda Yosefa Awe dkk, *Kurikulum Pendidikan* (Sumatera Barat: CV.Pratama Azka, 2021), hal 13.

⁸Dwi Rahdiyanta, "Kurikulum(KBK) Berbasis Kompetensi," 2003, hal 6.

⁹*ibid*

¹⁰Nikolaus Anggal and Yohanes Yuda dkk, *Manajemen Pendidikan: Penggunaan Sumber Daya Secara Efektif Untuk Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan* (Gunawana Lestari, 2020), hal 112.

¹¹Baharuddin, *Studi Kebijakan Pendidikan Agama Islam* (Malang: Media Nusa Creative, 2022), hal 81.

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programs. Competencies taught are in accordance with national education goals, and competencies include attitudes, skills and knowledge as a whole.

The Merdeka Curriculum offers more optimal content and diverse learning variations, allowing students to deepen concepts and improve their skills with sufficient time. Teachers are given the freedom to choose teaching tools that suit students' learning needs and interests. Students have many options based on their aspirations and skills, giving them personal freedom and discretion.¹² The Merdeka curriculum aims to provide education that emphasizes competence and character by prioritizing national and universal values. Apart from that, this curriculum also focuses on developing skills to face changing times. With a focus on competency and academic achievement, this curriculum has many advantages compared to the previous one, including increasing students' ability to compete globally. The Merdeka curriculum not only focuses on developing skills to face modern-day challenges but also on developing competencies and improving academic achievement. Unlike the previous curriculum, this curriculum has many advantages, including increasing students' ability to compete at the global level. Apart from that, another goal is to create a young generation that has an open, critical, and innovative mind. Better known as the prototype curriculum, it is implemented by schools in driving school programs and independently in some school.¹³

Education Curriculum in South Korea

Education in South Korea aims to instill a sense of national identity and respect for national sovereignty, improve the personality of citizens, uphold the ideals of universal brotherhood, develop independence, and encourage contributions to a democratic state and global prosperity. The South Korean education system consists of four levels, namely elementary school, middle school, high school and higher education. Each level has its duration and focus; for example, primary school is mandatory for six years with a high graduation rate, while junior high school is a continuation of elementary school and lasts for three years. High school is available in two options, general and vocational, covering fields such as agriculture, commerce, fishing and engineering. There are also comprehensive schools that combine general and vocational aspects in preparation for further education at college or university. Higher education includes undergraduate programs and postgraduate programs such as master's and doctoral degrees.

Since 1970, Korea has reformed its educational curriculum with a focus on incorporating classroom learning techniques and the use of technology. Teachers carry out five important steps, starting from teaching planning, student diagnosis, student learning guidance through programs, and testing to assessing learning outcomes (evaluation). In contrast, in secondary schools, entrance tests are removed to implement the equal accessibility policy. In 2012, Korea made major changes to the education system, especially in the PAUD sector, by implementing the Nuri Curriculum. This curriculum aims to enable children to find happiness and achieve their hopes and dreams. The Nuri curriculum combines the national kindergarten curriculum and the national childcare curriculum and emphasizes five aspects of child development, including sports, communication, art, play, and interaction with nature. The achievement standards of the Nuri Curriculum include the development of physical abilities, communication skills, respect for oneself and others, stimulation of interest and creativity in the arts, and the formation of a scientific attitude and curiosity in everyday life. The Nuri Curriculum aims to improve interpersonal communication skills, strengthen collaboration skills, stimulate children's interest in nature and art, and enrich children's knowledge about the world.¹⁴

Curriculum system in Korea There is no entrance exam for junior high schools. It is due to the policy of the regional mayor or governor towards secondary schools in the area. The Korean curriculum is published by KICE (Korean Curriculum Evaluation Institute) and includes a standard curriculum that consists of the Korean language, arts, code of ethics, social studies, mathematics, science, health and physical education, music, and English. South Korea is currently implementing an educational program that provides competency and prepares knowledge for the world of work and skills to move on to the next level. The curriculum is developed by the education/school committee based on the characteristics of the learning environment, students, and region, taking into account global developments. The curriculum in public and private schools is relatively the same; teaching more independence, creativity, and socialization within the environment teaches daily life and the development of science and technology. Schools can add local subjects based on student's interests and the situation in their region, as well as choose local subjects that focus on agriculture and fisheries issues and technology that can foster student creativity, especially those that can foster student creativity. Beneficial to their lives.¹⁵

In South Korea, the implementation of the local curriculum is different from that in Indonesia. Usually, the local curriculum in Indonesia includes material that is not directly related to students' daily lives, such as regional or foreign languages, arts, etc., without considering students' wishes or the local situation in their area. South Korea also emphasizes the importance of education very strongly. Students there face enormous pressure to achieve academic success. They spend time at school from morning until

¹²Ayi Suherman, *Implementasi Kurikulum Merdeka* (Bandung: Indonesia emas group, 2023), hal 2.

¹³Erna Labudasari and Eliya Rochmah, *Kurikulum Merdeka: teori dan praktik di sekolah* (Bandung: Indonesia Group Emas, 2023), hal 4.

¹⁴Ernawati Harahap, *Inovasi Kurikulum* (Jawa Tengah: Penerbit NEM, 2022), hal 84.

¹⁵Destri Wulandari and Hilmin dkk, "Sistem Pendidikan Korea Selatan Dan Indonesia," *Jurnal Studi Islam Indonesia*, Vol. 1 No.1 (2023): hal 26.

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late at night, followed by additional education to improve academic performance. The main focus is preparation for highly competitive college entrance exams, with the aim of supporting students' futures.¹⁶

South Korea is known for its high industrial productivity, ranking 11th out of 50 countries in the statistics. Apart from that, this country also broke the record for the highest growth in Asia. Despite having a solid economy, South Korea attracts attention in education because its system is recognized globally. The collectivist approach to teaching and the values espoused in South Korean society has made it recognized as a superior and advanced system.¹⁷

Therefore, South Korea now provides the necessary competencies for participants to be ready to enter the world of work, and the country places great emphasis on the importance of education, which can be seen by the high focus on students. Students have had to spend time at school from morning until midnight for years. It is due to the need to attend additional educational programs to improve their academic performance. Higher education is also a priority for students, with rigorous selection to ensure their future.¹⁸

South Korea's education system is superior because it has achieved a literacy rate of 100%, as well as good performance in analysis and critical thinking tests. Teachers also receive high respect and are even considered equal to holy figures. The situation in Indonesia is different, with a lack of teacher respect. They are often seen as heroes without recognition and only as guardians of children at school. Teachers in South Korea are known to be firm and harsh in educating students, even using corporal punishment to teach lessons. However, this practice cannot be implemented in Indonesia because it violates human rights (HAM). Sometimes, if teachers in Indonesia give physical punishment, they will be blamed, even though the student did wrong.

The goal is to obtain resources that can improve the educational environment, teacher performance, and quality of education. The education autonomy law was approved in 1990, creating councils at provincial and national levels. The board of education acts as the legislative body, while the superintendent of education serves as the head of the executive organization. Regional supervisors are part of regional autonomy granted by the central government.

To reshape the teacher culture system, the South Korean government is accelerating teacher training to get schools back on track. As part of these efforts, teacher training centers were established for primary and secondary education institutions, and teaching certificates were awarded to teachers who completed training courses in secondary schools. In 1973, teacher training centers for primary schools were abolished due to changes in affiliation with tertiary institutions.

At that time, South Korea established the Korea National University of Education to carry out three main educational functions: teacher development, teacher training, and educational research. With these three primary functions' existence, progress in education and teaching occurs, and teachers' thinking patterns develop in the teaching context. The education system in South Korea includes early childhood education (PAUD), primary education (SD), secondary education (SMP), higher education, and lifelong education. In the South Korean education system, nine years of compulsory education are implemented, covering primary to secondary education. In 2019, there were 8,837 kindergartens, 6,087 elementary schools (including 74 private schools, or 1.2%), and 5,570 secondary schools (with 1,581 private schools, or 28.4%).

The South Korean higher education development strategy includes three main approaches: a systematic approach, which involves structured planning, implementation, and evaluation of policies; a multilevel approach, which emphasizes priorities from primary education to higher education levels; and a sequential approach, which emphasizes expanding primary education despite the potential to create overcrowded classes, as well as a policy of equalizing high school by eliminating senior high school entrance exams.¹⁹

Since 1969, South Korea has abolished junior high school entrance exams, allowing 99.2% of elementary school graduates to continue their education to middle school. In 1973, a similar policy was implemented for senior high school entrance exams. However, university entrance exams remain a prerequisite. At the junior high school level, two evaluation exams are held every semester, and the results are sent to each student's home. When entering the third grade, students' grades and abilities will be considered to continue at senior high school. At this stage, the homeroom teacher advises and guides students to continue to high school.

¹⁶Hawa Rani Sukma and Achmad Hufad dkk, "Analisis Perbandingan Kurikulum Pendidikan Korea Selatan Dan Indonesia" Vol 06, No 02, no. Journal on education (2024): hal 12750.

¹⁷Diaz Putri Amelia, Kolektivitas dalam Nomenklatur Pendidikan Moral di Korea Selatan, Vol. 1 No. 8 Agustus 2021. Hal 264-270

¹⁸Hawa Rani Sukma, Analisis Perbandingan Kurikulum Pendidikan Korea Selatan dan Indonesia, Vol 06, No. 02, Januari-Februari 2024 Hal 12749-12750

¹⁹Komaruddin Sassi, Sistem Pendidikan DI Korea Selatan, Vol.4, No.4 November 2023. Hal 55-83

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The evaluation in South Korea is known as College Scholastic Aptitude (CSAT) at the senior high school level, which KICE supervises. The exam covers five subjects, including Korean language, mathematics, English, social sciences, natural sciences, and vocational sciences (according to major), and students can choose one foreign language, such as classical Chinese. Students are considered to have passed if their score is in the range of 0-200 with a minimum score of 100, while for major subjects, the minimum score is 50. Therefore, the total minimum score required to graduate is 250. The assessment for entering university combines achievements during high school and scores from the national scholastic exam (Su-Neung). Reports during senior high school have 40% weight in determining graduation.

The educational structure in South Korea is similar to that in Indonesia. Starting from the following:

1. Kindergarten (TK) in Korea Kindergarten is not a formal program but a private institution that teaches Korean and English.
2. Elementary School (Chodeunghakgyo) lasts for six years, aged 7-13 years. While in elementary school, students in grades 1 and 2 learn Korean, Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, Arts, and English. Meanwhile, for grades 3 to 6, PE, moral education, practical arts, and music are added.
3. Education at South Korean Junior High School (Junghakgyo) lasts for three years, starting from grades 7 to 9, with students aged around 12 or 13 when they enter and graduating at around 15 or 16 years old. Like in Indonesia, middle school in South Korea is also a transition phase to adulthood that demands discipline and compliance with school rules. Students have a daily schedule with six subjects and often take additional lessons after school. Learning materials include mathematics, English, Korean, social studies, and natural sciences as core subjects, with additional subjects such as music, art, sports, history, ethics, home economics, technology, and Hanja. Each lesson lasts 45 minutes, with extra time before class starts for independent study, watching the Education Broadcast System (EBS), or other activities.
4. College/High School (Godeunghakgyo) is a 3-year level of education, with grades 10-12 and an entry age of around 15 or 16 years, while graduating at around 17-19 years. There are two tracks at this level: a specialized track that suits interests, such as science, foreign languages, or the arts, with highly competitive entrance exams similar to those seen in the Korean drama "Dream High." Additionally, there is a choice between general schools, comparable to high schools in Indonesia, and vocational schools, such as agriculture, commerce, fishing, and engineering. This vocational school places more emphasis on preparing students for work after graduation.
5. Higher education in South Korea consists of grades 13-16 at the university level (S1) or academic high school (junior college) and then proceed to postgraduate programs (S2/S3). The academic year is divided into two semesters: the first semester, starting from early March to mid-July, with a summer holiday between mid-July and late August, and the second semester, starting from late August to mid-February, with a winter holiday. Second-semester exams are usually held from late December to early February, with graduation in mid-February (for one week), while the start of the second semester starts from mid-February to early March

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In general, it will be discussed how the educational curriculum in Indonesia and South Korea compares in terms of several aspects.

1) Goals

The aim of national education in Indonesia is to produce individuals who have high moral qualities, who adhere firmly to religious values and Pancasila, and are able to contribute to improving culture and developing democracy as responsible citizens.²⁰

Meanwhile, in South Korea's educational goals, one of the decisions taken by the National Council of the Republic of Korea in 1948 was creating an education law. In this context, education in South Korea aims to inspire a sense of national identity and respect for national sovereignty in every individual, form a perfect personality for every citizen, instill a universal spirit of brotherhood, develop skills for independent living, and contribute to a democratic state and welfare of all mankind, as well as fostering an attitude of patriotism.²¹

2) Learning Time

In Indonesia, school study hours usually start in the morning, around 6:30 am to 9:00 am. Generally, students in Indonesia study at school from 7 am to noon for Elementary School and 7 am to 1.30 pm for Junior High School. Meanwhile, Senior High School must be present from 7 in the morning until 2.30 pm. These times do not include additional tutoring or extra study time the school arranges. Thus, on average, students in Indonesia spend around 7.5 hours studying at school per day.

Meanwhile, regarding school times in South Korea, education is the main priority, as reflected in the students' study schedule, which starts at 7 am and continues until late at night. They attend school and take additional courses outside of school hours to prepare for highly competitive college entrance exams. As a result, students aged 13-18 in South Korea spend most of their day in the study

²⁰Romi Mesra and Paulus Robert Taulah, "Studi Komparatif Sistem Pendidikan Di Korea Selatan Dengan Indonesia" Vol 1, No 1, no. Jurnal Pendidikan Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial (2024): hal 22.

²¹Ismail Eka Wijaya, "Studi Komparatif Pendidikan Di Kawasan Asia(RRC,KOREA SELATAN,JEPANG)," jurnal pendidikan dan budaya, Vol 5, No 1 (207AD): hal 53.

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room, with extended study hours and extra courses that last until late at night until their daily time is spent studying rather than relaxing.

3) Education Management

Education management in Indonesia covers many areas, including curriculum planning, resource management, improving teacher competency, and assessing learning outcomes. However, challenges remain, such as the gap between urban and rural areas and the need to improve access to and quality of education for everyone.

Meanwhile, Education Management in South Korea involves giving authority to the minister of education, while at the regional level, there is an education council consisting of seven members. These members are elected by local areas, with some having official positions held by local mayors or governors. The mayor or governor leads the education board.²²

4) Learning Process

In Indonesia, the Merdeka Curriculum aims to respond to the challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, emphasizing critical thinking, creativity, innovation, communication, and collaboration skills. The Merdeka Curriculum allows students to explore various learning areas, deepening their concepts and strengthening their competencies. Teachers also have the flexibility to choose teaching materials that suit the needs and interests of students.

Meanwhile, in South Korea, KICE (Korea Institute of Curriculum and Evaluation) compiles a standard curriculum that includes the Korean language, arts, ethics, social sciences, mathematics, natural sciences, health and physical education, music, and English. The main focus of the curriculum in South Korea is to provide skills needed for the world of work and preparation for further education. Although both have local content curricula, the approach and focus are different; in South Korea, the local content curriculum is directly related to meeting students' living needs, while in Indonesia, it is more limited to regional languages, foreign languages, and arts as part of efforts to preserve local culture.

5) Teacher

In Indonesia, teachers have no transfer rotation after five years of teaching. Teachers assigned to a school will remain at that school until they retire. To become a lecturer in Indonesia, the minimum qualification required is a master's degree to teach at the undergraduate level, while to teach at the master's level, a doctoral degree is required, and so on, with higher qualifications than the level being taught.

Meanwhile, in South Korea, there are two forms of teacher education: academic level for elementary school teachers and four years of education for secondary school teachers. The government is responsible for the costs of public teacher education. The teachers will obtain certificates, such as preschool teacher, primary school teacher, and secondary teacher certificates, which the principal awards in various categories, including apprentice teachers, regular teachers, and licenses for apprentice teachers who have passed the four-year program graduate qualification exam in the fields of engineering, fisheries, trade, and agriculture. In South Korea, after five years of teaching, teachers undergo a rotation of transfers to provide a fair opportunity for each teacher to teach in various schools, both qualified and not. To become a lecturer at a junior-level university, the qualification required is a master's degree with two years of experience, while to become a lecturer at a senior-level university, the qualification required is a doctorate.

6) Assessment

In Indonesia, in the Minister of National Education Regulation Number 20 of 2007, it is stated that in the education unit level curriculum, assessment is based on specific criteria that determine the measurement of competency achievement. This means that the education unit must establish minimum completion criteria (KKM) for each subject to assess student competency. KKM is a guide for teachers in assessing students' competencies according to the essential competencies of the subjects they are taking and for students to prepare themselves to take subject assessments.

Meanwhile, in South Korea, since 1969, it has abolished junior and senior high school entrance exams, allowing almost all elementary school graduates to continue their education at that level. Even so, university entrance exams are still required. In junior high school, two-semester evaluations provide information to students and parents. In contrast, in grade 3, the decision to continue to high school is based on assessing the student's grades and abilities, with guidance from the homeroom teacher. The high school exam, known as College Scholastic Aptitude (CSAT), covers five subjects, and the minimum score required to pass is 250, weighing 40% of the assessments throughout high school.

7) Educational Examination

Indonesia has a national exam at the Senior High School level known as the National Exam. This exam assesses students' understanding of the subject matter and determines their educational path. However, the Indonesian government is currently trying to change the national examination system to a more comprehensive assessment system.

²²Cepi Riyana, *Studi Perbandingan Kurikulum Cina, Korea, Dan Jepang*, 2008, hal 9.

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Meanwhile, in South Korea, the educational evaluation system is very competitive, primarily through a national exam called Suneung, which significantly impacts a student's chances of being accepted at the college of his choice. The exam is held every year in November; Suneung determines a student's future because the results affect their acceptance into college. This exam is very competitive and is considered one of the most critical moments in a Korean student's life. Apart from that, there are also other exams at the Korean student level at school, such as mid-term exams and end-of-year exams

CONCLUSION

This research includes several findings, including 1) The goals of education in Indonesia and South Korea both emphasize the importance of building national identity, improving individual quality, and contributing to the country's and society's development. The curriculum in South Korea is revised every 5-10 years, whereas in Indonesia, every time leadership changes. 3) The education system in South Korea tends to use a more formal learning approach which is teacher-centered and uses exercises and exams, whereas in Indonesia, the learning approach is more student-centered and uses group discussions as a learning method. 4) Educators in South Korea do a better job than in Indonesia. Students study from early morning until late at night and take additional courses to participate in competitive college entrance exams. As a result, students aged 13-18 years in South Korea spend most of their day in class. In Indonesia, classes usually start at 6:30 to 9:00 a.m. In Indonesia, students go to school from seven in the morning to noon for elementary school students and from seven in the morning to one in the afternoon for junior high school students. High school students must be present from seven in the morning until half past two in the afternoon. These times do not include additional lectures or study time the school arranges. In Indonesia, students spend an average of 7.5 hours a day studying at school. 5) Middle school entrance exams were abolished in South Korea, allowing almost all elementary school students to move on to the next stage. In 1973, a similar policy was implemented for secondary schools. However, university entrance exams are still required, and in Indonesia, Senior High School Level students undergo the National Examination. However, the government is currently trying to make the assessment system more comprehensive.

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